

Sensing of Tb^{III} and Eu^{III} in aqueous medium by a phenanthroline based ligand

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Abstract : A simple phenanthroline based fluorescent receptor (PTRIS) has been shown to act as a sensor for the recognition of Tb^{III} and Eu^{III} in absolute water. UV-Vis absorption as well as fluorescence studies support the recognition phenomena. The complexation of these lanthanides with PTRIS has been proven by the changes of phosphorescence emission related to the metal centre. Strong complexation has been found for Tb^{III} and PTRIS resulting in very strong turn-on phosphorescence effect related to Tb^{III}.

Keywords : Phenanthroline based receptor, fluorescent sensor, Eu^{III}, Tb^{III} sensors, water soluble.

Introduction

Lanthanides are well known as rare earth elements. A minute quantity of these elements is present in earth's crust. Almost all the lanthanides occur as intractable mixture in nature. So they are very hard to separate from each other. Like other metals europium has a bright silvery appearance. It is very reactive in nature. It forms its oxide in presence of oxygen in air. So it is stored under mineral oil. Like other rare earth cousins terbium is not so reactive. It reacts comparatively slowly with oxygen to form its oxide. The lanthanides are characterized by uniform (III) oxidation state which is most stable and common. The 4f electrons in the antepenultimate shell are very effectively shielded from their chemical environment outside the atom by the 5s and 5p electrons and 4f electrons thus do not take part in bonding and they are not removed to produce ions and they do not take any significant part in crystal field stabilization of complexes. The electronic configurations and radii of

the Tb³⁺ and Eu³⁺ are [Xe] 4f⁸ and 4f⁶ respectively with radii 0.923 Å and 0.947 Å. Lanthanide elements are sometimes used as biological tracers for drugs in humans and animals. This is because lanthanide elements can quite easily be studied in the body by spectroscopy because their peaks are narrow as well as very characteristic. Eu is the most reactive in the lanthanide series and makes +3 and +2 compounds. Eu has also use in superconductivity. Europium oxide is widely used as a doping agent in phosphorous in television sets and computer monitors. Valency three Eu produces a red radiance and valency two Eu produces a blue radiance and when both valencies are combined a white light is produced which is used in compact fluorescent bulbs/the yellow/green terbium phosphorous give "white" light.

In recent decades there is an upsurge of interest in supramolecular chemistry for the lanthanide complexes¹⁻⁹ which are well-known for their interesting magnetic and luminescent properties¹⁰⁻¹³.

A number of applications as functional molecular devices have been taken place based on these properties in the fields of chemistry, material science, biology and medicine e.g. europium complexes are used as the chemical shift reagents in NMR spectroscopy, as a red phosphor, in fluorescent lamps etc.¹⁴⁻¹⁸. Among all these signal transduction methods, detection by fluorescence technique has received much attention because of their sensitivity with different types of physicochemical interactions that can be used in different cases to modulate the emission level¹⁹⁻²¹. Herein we report water soluble phenanthroline based receptor PTRIS that can act as a sensor for Tb^{III} and Eu^{III} in 1 mM HEPES buffer (pH 7.0). The extended imine system present in this podand is responsible for a perfect geometry required for binding as well as complexation of the above mentioned lanthanides. This sensor has the unique combination of ring nitrogen, side chain imino nitrogen as well as aliphatic hydroxyl groups to coordinate to the metal ion [Tb^{III} or Eu^{III}] in the matching cavity of the ligand.

Results and discussion

PTRIS (Fig. 1) has been synthesized (Scheme 1) starting from very useful synthetic precursor 1,10-phenanthroline-2,9-dicarboxaldehyde according to the procedure published by Chandler *et al.*²². Imine formation reaction of the mentioned dicarboxaldehyde and the amine yielded the desired product, PTRIS. Neocuproine is first oxidized with selenium dioxide in dioxane-water solvent mixture under refluxing condition for 2 h to furnish the dicarboxaldehyde, which was then treated with tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane in dry methanol at room temperature for 4 h to afford the imine in an excellent yield of 95%. The ligand has been characterized using NMR. Tb^{III}, Eu^{III} require 8 coordination (donor) sites and these metal centers are relatively larger in size. According to Pearson's hard and soft acid-base theory trivalent lanthanides are considered as hard Lewis acids. Hence in the designed ligand PTRIS 6 -OH moieties can act as donors to the above mentioned lanthanides. Again the soft phenanthroline nitrogen atoms have possibility

Fig. 1. Structure of PTRIS and it's probable complex with Eu³⁺ and Tb³⁺ respectively.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of PTRIS : Reagents and conditions : (i) SeO₂, dioxane-H₂O, 2 h, reflux; (ii) tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane, MeOH, rt, 4 h, 95%.

to fulfill the rest two required donor sites for them. The imine nitrogen atoms also can take part in the chelation with the metal centre. Thus PTRIS is an ideal ligand for the targeted lanthanides. The sensor binds effectively more Tb^{III} and this simple sensor has unique combination of rigid phenanthroline ring nitrogens along with side chain imino nitrogens as well as three coordinative hydroxyl groups in flexible arms positioned suitably to bind to Tb^{III} and Eu^{III} respectively. Since Tb^{III} is somewhat smaller compared to Eu^{III} having ionic radii 0.92 Å and 0.95 Å respectively, Tb^{III} binds better with the sensor PTRIS according to the cavity size of this specific phenanthroline ligand.

Meanwhile 25 ml 1.0 × 10⁻⁵ M solution of PTRIS containing 1 mM HEPES buffer (pH 7.0), 10 ml 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M solutions of Eu^{III} and Tb^{III} as their triflate salts were prepared in distilled water. These stock solutions were used for all UV-Vis, fluorescence and phosphorescence studies.

UV-Vis absorption studies :

PTRIS itself exhibits λ_{max} at 278 nm and 231 nm due to the n-π* and π-π* transitions of phenanthroline moiety which can be found in the UV-Vis absorption spectra (Fig. 2). Addition of Tb^{III} and Eu^{III} shifts strongly the former bands. Binding constant²³ (K_a) calculated for PTRIS and Tb^{III} is 1.61 × 10⁴ M⁻¹ and of Eu^{III} in UV-Vis absorption method is 1.55 × 10⁴ M⁻¹.

Job plot experiments (Fig. 3) have been performed to understand the binding mode between host and guest which confirm 1 : 1 binding.

Luminescence studies :

Fluorescence studies :

The fluorescence emission related to the phenanthroline moiety is also affected due to the binding phenomenon. Prominent turn-off effect of the phenanthroline backbone is found in both of the cases (Fig. 4) when excited at 278 nm. Binding constant²⁴

Fig. 2. (a) UV-Vis absorption study of PTRIS and Tb^{III}; (b) UV-Vis absorption study of PTRIS and Eu^{III} in H₂O.

(K_a) determined by fluorescence method for PTRIS and Tb^{III} is 12.04 × 10⁵ M⁻¹ and of Eu^{III} is 7.28 × 10⁵ M⁻¹.

Binding curves (Fig. 5) plotted against lanthanide concentration and ratio of changes of intensities in fluorescence appears to be 1 : 1 binding between the host and the guest.

Phosphorescence studies :

In situ formation of PTRIS lanthanide complexation has been studied by the changes in ground state of PTRIS and the phosphorescence spectra (Fig. 6) of Tb^{III} and Eu^{III} in H₂O. Tb^{III} and Eu^{III} exist as highly

Fig. 3. (a) Non-linear fit of Job plot of PTRIS and Tb^{III} in UV-Vis absorption method; (b) non-linear fit of Job plot of PTRIS and Eu^{III} in UV-Vis absorption method.

hydrated stable octa aqua complex excluding the capped water molecule in it. So it is really challenging to compete with these water molecules to kick away these bound waters to form more stable lanthanide complex. The complexation has been shown to be the best for Tb^{III} and the least for Eu^{III}. Very strong turn-on effect in phosphorescence emission has been observed in case of PTRIS when titrated with Tb^{III}. This turn-on effect due to addition of increasing amount of Tb^{III} proves strong and quick complexation between these two.

Due to presence of 4f⁸ orbital Tb^{III} has some interesting properties. As it has more than 7 valence

Fig. 4. (a) Fluorescence study of PTRIS and Tb^{III} in H₂O; (b) fluorescence study of PTRIS and Eu^{III} in H₂O.

electrons, both high spin and low spin 4f⁷5d¹ electronic configurations are possible depending on the coordinated ligands. The low-spin configuration has higher energy than high-spin configuration. So under these circumstances transitions between ⁷D_J to ⁷F₆ are spin allowed and transitions between ⁹D_J to ⁷F₆ are spin forbidden^{25,26}.

From the phosphorescence spectra (obtained by exciting at 278 nm) it can be concluded that phenanthroline antenna successfully populates the Tb^{III} ⁵D₄ excited state with emission signature at 488.95, 546.02, 586.02, 622.02 nm corresponding to ⁵D₄ to

Fig. 5. (a) Binding graph PTRIS and Tb^{III} in fluorescence method; (b) binding graph PTRIS and Eu^{III} in fluorescence method.

⁷F_J ($J = 6-3$) deactivation. The similar phenomenon occurs for Eu³⁺ but less effectively. These transitions for Eu³⁺ corresponds to ⁵D₄ to ⁷F_J ($J = 0-4$) giving rise to the emission signature at 592.05, 614.05, 651.01, 698.00 nm.

Conclusion

In conclusion we have successfully designed a simple fluorescent sensor PTRIS which can form strong complex with Tb^{III} compared to Eu^{III} in aqueous solution. Complexation has been depicted by the UV-Vis, fluorescence and phosphorescence studies.

Fig. 6. (a) Phosphorescence study of PTRIS and Tb^{III} in H₂O; (b) phosphorescence study of PTRIS and Eu^{III} in H₂O.

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